

An Information Based Theory of Stationary Action and the Origin of Quantum Phenomena

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The quantization of energy proposed by Planck to account for the observed spectrum of black body radiation has associated with it a quantization of entropy. This in turn implies a quantization of observable information, directly implying observational uncertainty on the order of Planck's constant. The effect of that uncertainty is analyzed. In order to adhere strictly to the use of observable quantities, a probability measure is employed based on the distinguishability of statistical samples. This leads directly to the description of probability in terms of the absolute square of a complex amplitude. The Feynman rules may then be applied naturally for indistinguishable events without contradiction to the conventional rules for distinguishable events. This enables the straightforward calculation of the probability that a particle moves from one arbitrary point to another. The Feynman formulation of non-relativistic quantum mechanics and the principle of stationary action results when it is assumed that the classical action represents the measure of distinguishability. Parallel analysis on a Lorentz manifold yields the geodesic principle. The entropic nature of uncertainty allows for the existence of hidden underlying physical processes analogous to the way statistical physics underlies the continuum gas model. This results in the observer experiencing randomness as a result of deficient information. The amplitude is then a representation of the state of the available information about the physical state of the system, rather than the physical state proper. We discuss how this helps to understand a number of the perplexing peculiarities of quantum behavior.

Introduction

Early efforts to understand black body radiation within the confines of classical physics focused on the entropy of electromagnetic radiation. In 1884 Boltzmann studied black body radiation in a perfectly reflecting enclosure. Treating the radiation pressure as that of a continuum gas he was able to define its entropy [1]. From that followed a theoretical basis for Stefan's empirically determined dependence of total radiated power on the fourth power of temperature.

Several years earlier Boltzmann had shown a correspondence between classical entropy and the discrete quantity that was later termed the *statistical multiplicity* [2] of a molecular gas, though he made no use of this in his black body work. It was not until the mid-twentieth century introduction of information theory [3] that entropy could be understood as information lost due to the statistical treatment of trajectories in lieu of a more complete microscopic model of molecular states [4].

By 1900, Planck had developed a classical model of the entropy of a black body at temperature T in which electromagnetic dipole resonators operated in equilibrium with the radiant energy in Boltzmann's reflective enclosure. Comparing the latest empirical data to his model, he found it necessary to introduce the constant h limiting radiation energy to discrete increments of $h\nu$ [5]. This quantization of energy has the effect of limiting the entropy to increments of $h\nu/T$ when expressed in the prevailing units, those of Boltzmann's constant k .

The appearance of entropy in discrete increments is consistent with the situation in statistical mechanics. As in the case of the continuum gas model, discrete entropy in the black body model may be interpreted as a paucity of accurate information. The continuous valued entropy of the classical model is then replaced by discrete values as was the case with Boltzmann's derivation of the entropy of a molecular gas.

Consider an ideal gas consisting of a single molecule. The Planck entropy implies an inability of the classical model to describe its trajectory in phase space with uncertainty less than h . Then the description of observable quantities in the classical model, like that of a continuum gas is only approximate, with the action of observed natural phenomena differing from the classical description. The result is an observed stochastic component of order h in the molecular trajectory.

It may be that a more accurate description of the trajectory is not possible. We will refer to this as *inherent randomness*. Alternatively, the trajectory may be fully deterministic but some inherent limit on observational accuracy produces the uncertainty h , even with perfectly accurate measuring equipment. We will refer to this as *apparent randomness*. In either case the result is an observed stochastic component of order h in the molecular trajectory.

We will examine the entropy H_k and the information I_k in three cases $k = 1,2,3$ representing respectively the inherently random case, the classical case, and the apparently random case. The subscripts are so arranged that the information necessary for a full description of a corresponding state in each model increases with the subscript.

In this situation, Planck's constant h is a more convenient unit of entropy. Let η be a system dependent parameter, then let

$$I_k = \eta h \tag{1}$$

represent the *additional* accurate information about natural phenomena provided by the k^{th} case over its lower indexed neighbor. In the apparently random case, there are one or more hidden variables requiring additional information I_3 over the classical model to produce a fully deterministic representation of quantum phenomena. Let H_3 represent the entropy of the more accurate case and H_2 the entropy of the classical case. Then, since information corresponds to negative entropy [6]

$$H_3 = H_2 - I_3 \tag{2}$$

and, since all of these quantities are positive, $H_3 < H_2$. If the more accurate model is both fully deterministic and completely accurate $H_3 = 0$ and then $H_2 = I_3$. Given the current state of knowledge of quantum phenomena, it should be born in mind that any more deterministic model of particle behavior must conform to Bell's theorem which preserves the nonlocal nature of that behavior.

Alternatively, in the inherently random case there are no hidden variables. Then the physical properties defined by classical canonically conjugate variables cannot be deterministically modeled to arbitrary precision despite their overdetermined description in the classical model. Analogous to (2) we have

$$H_2 = H_1 - I_2 \tag{3}$$

where I_2 represents the misinformation in the classical description. Because the information it represents is invalid, I_2 is represented by a negative number and thus contributes positively to the entropy of the classical model. Now we have $H_2 > H_1$. If the quantum model is the most accurate model of nature possible, we have $H_1 = 0$ and then $H_2 = -I_2$. Whether the apparently random or inherently random case prevails over the classical one, the prevailing case is the lower entropy one.

The analysis that follows explicitly acknowledges statistical uncertainties in observations of physical systems. Following classical practice, we assume no explicit limit on the accuracy of measuring instruments. Also, as in the classical view, the explicit effect of a measurement is assumed in advance to have no significant impact on the result.

The existence of uncertainty requires that the inherently stochastic nature of the result of observation be incorporated in the analysis. The choice of probability measure can be of profound importance [7]. Since our central concern involves a difference between what may actually exist and what can be observed, careful attention is paid to ensuring our analysis is based strictly on what can be observed. To that end we employ a probability measure based on stochastic outcomes that are equal in statistical distinguishability from one another.

Distinguishing one experimental outcome from another is necessarily a matter of distinguishing between their probability distributions. The distinguishability of probability distributions has been quantified by Fisher [8]. Wootters has employed the term *statistical distance* for that quantity and studied its properties along continuous paths. He has also shown that the angle between rays in Hilbert space measures the statistical distance between the pure quantum states the rays represent [9].

Consider two N sided loaded dice with slightly different loadings, where the differences in the probabilities of corresponding faces are $\delta p_1 \cdots \delta p_N$. In an instance of the Cramer Rao bound [10], the dice are said to be distinguishable in n trials if [9]

$$\frac{\sqrt{n}}{2} \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(\delta p_i)^2}{p_i} \right] > 1 \quad (4)$$

The N probabilities p_1, \dots, p_N of each element of the set of all possible N sided loaded dice define an $N - 1$ dimensional probability simplex embedded in an N dimensional space of real numbers. The simplex is defined by the restriction that the necessarily nonnegative probabilities of each die sum to unity.

Then the statistical distance \mathcal{S} between two dice with arbitrarily large differences in the N probabilities is defined along the shortest path between their two locations on the simplex as follows [9]:

$$\mathcal{S} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \times \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{the maximum number of intermediate outcomes each of} \\ \text{which is distinguishable (in } n \text{ trials) from its neighbors} \end{array} \right] \quad (5)$$

The same definition applies to the statistical length of an arbitrary path $p_i(t)$ between points on the simplex. That statistical length is then

$$d\mathcal{S}(t) = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{p_i(t)} \left[\frac{dp_i(t)}{dt} \right]^2 \right\}^{1/2} dt \quad (6)$$

This formulation may be simplified by the substitution $\zeta_i \equiv p_i^{1/2}$. Then [9]

$$d\mathcal{S}(t) = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{d\zeta_i(t)}{dt} \right]^2 \right\}^{1/2} dt \quad (7)$$

Analysis

Let $x = (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3)$ represent the ordinary space and time of classical physics where x_0 represents time and x_1, x_2 and x_3 represent three-dimensional Euclidean space. Let us consider a particle that moves from start point A to end point B by an unknown trajectory through this space and time. Let $x(t)$ be an arbitrary trajectory with the same end points, where t is a time like parameter. We stipulate, in view of uncertainty, that for any value of the parameter t assigning a definite time and place on $x(t)$ there may be a nonzero probability $p(x, t)$ that the particle can be observed at any time and place x . We further stipulate that this probability distribution may vary with the parameter t .

Let $p(x, t)$ be piecewise differentiable with respect to t and again $\zeta \equiv p^{1/2}$. From (7) the statistical distance between points on $x(t)$ in the physical space may then be expressed as the statistical distance \mathcal{S} between corresponding points on the associated probability simplex.

$$d\mathcal{S}(t) = \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 \iiint_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \left[\frac{d\zeta(x, t)}{dt} \right]^2 \right\}^{1/2} dt \quad (8)$$

This expression defines an element of length $d\mathcal{S}$ in an infinite dimensional Euclidean ζ space described in rectilinear coordinates [9]. Since $\zeta^2(x, t)$ is a probability, it's integral over all of space and time is unity for any value of the parameter t . Thus $d\mathcal{S}$ lies on the surface of an infinite dimensional unit hypersphere. This constitutes a probability simplex embedded in ζ space, with each point on it representing a distinct probability distribution.

Then statistical length \mathcal{S} on a trajectory in space and time $x(t)$ is measured by the length of the arc traced on the surface of the unit hypersphere as the progress of parameter t traces out the trajectory [9]. As the location of the particle in physical space unfolds with increasing t the probability distribution $p(x, t)$ changes as well with the corresponding change in position on the surface of the hypersphere.

Now let us divide the integral on the right-hand-side of (8) in two. Let $[da(t)/dt]^2$ represent the portion of the integral for which $x_0 < t$ and $[db(t)/dt]^2$ the portion for which $x_0 > t$.

$$\left[\frac{da}{dt}\right]^2 \equiv \int_{-\infty}^t dx_0 \iiint_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \left[\frac{d\zeta(x, t)}{dt}\right]^2 \quad (9)$$

$$\left[\frac{db}{dt}\right]^2 \equiv \int_t^{\infty} dx_0 \iiint_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \left[\frac{d\zeta(x, t)}{dt}\right]^2 \quad (10)$$

Then

$$d\mathcal{S}(t) = \left\{ \left[\frac{da(t)}{dt}\right]^2 + \left[\frac{db(t)}{dt}\right]^2 \right\}^{1/2} dt \quad (11)$$

The substitutions (9) and (10) have been chosen such that (11) is identical in form to (7). This assures that a and b are root probabilities as are $\zeta_i(x, t)$ at each point in space and time. Since the probabilities at any value of t must still sum to unity, $a^2 + b^2 = 1$.

Analogous to (8) the unit hypersphere is collapsed into the unit circle, its two dimensions representing contributions to the probability from the past and future. The statistical distance \mathcal{S} between points on $x(t)$ may now be measured by the length of the arc traced on the new circular probability simplex on the real plane as the progress of parameter t traces out the trajectory $x(t)$ in space and time.

Since the right-hand side of (11) describes an element of arc length $d\theta(t)$ on the unit circle and is simultaneously equal to the right-hand side of (8)

$$d\mathcal{S}(t) = d\theta(t) \quad (12)$$

while $d\theta(t)$ is described in terms of $\zeta(x, t)$ by the right-hand side of (8). It is understood that the trajectory $x(t)$ may prescribe multiple circuits about the unit circle. Now, $a = \cos[\theta(t) + \theta_0]$ and $b = \sin[\theta(t) + \theta_0]$ where $\theta(t) = \int_{x(t)} d\theta$ and θ_0 is an arbitrary constant of integration. The arbitrary nature of θ_0 arises because a and b are not independent since the sum of their squares is fixed.

We proceed to form the complex quantity $a(t) + ib(t) = e^{i\theta(t)}$ representing the same unit circle probability simplex on the Argand plane. Then, in order to express the probability $p[x(t)]$ of our particle being found at a point on the trajectory $x(t)$ as an explicit function of the measure defined by statistical distance $\theta(t)$ we can now define the probability amplitude:

$$\varphi[x(t)] \equiv \zeta[x(t)]e^{i\theta(t)} \quad (13)$$

Then

$$p[x(t)] = |\varphi[x(t)]|^2 = \langle \varphi | \varphi \rangle \quad (14)$$

Representation of the probability in terms of a Hilbert space has the effect of including the real valued measure θ along with the real valued magnitude $|\varphi|$ in the statement of the probability expressed by the single complex variable φ [7].

The Feynman Rules

The identification of a probability with the absolute square of a complex quantity constitutes the Feynman *amplitude-probability rule* [11, 12].

While the Feynman rules are explicitly intended for the purpose of quantum mechanical calculation, the conditions assumed here in developing the probability amplitude consist of no more than a random variable with probability described by a function piecewise differentiable with respect to some parameter. This suggests we examine the possibility that the Feynman rules be treated as a feature of probability theory, when such events are indistinguishable.

Indeed the peculiarities of quantum theory that depend upon what can and cannot be measured may be regarded as depending upon distinguishability. It will be necessary of course to assure that the probability of indistinguishable events does not clash with the probability of distinguishable events.

The conventional Laplace rule for the probability p_L of an event that may occur by any of multiple alternative means is

$$p_L = \sum p_i = \sum |\varphi_i|^2 \quad (15)$$

where p_i represents the probability of each of the alternatives. The Laplace rules are empirical in nature, verified by counting occurrences of the various constituent events [13]. Alternatives can only be counted of course, when they are distinguishable. We know from a century of experience with quantum phenomena that when the alternatives are *indistinguishable* the probability p_F is [11].

$$p_F = |\varphi_F|^2 = \left| \sum \varphi_i \right|^2 \quad (16)$$

This constitutes the *Feynman amplitude sum rule* [12, 14].

The conventional Laplace rule for the probability p_L that multiple events all occur is

$$p_L = \prod p_i = \prod |\varphi_i|^2 \quad (17)$$

where p_i represents the probability of each of the multiple events. Experience with quantum phenomena informs us that when the multiple events are indistinguishable the probability p_F is now [11].

$$p_F = |\varphi_F|^2 = \left| \prod \varphi_i \right|^2 \quad (18)$$

This constitutes the *Feynman amplitude product rule* [12,14]. While the two formulae yield identical probabilities, the latter establishes the phase $\theta_F = \sum \theta_i$ for the composite event.

Goyal, Knuth and Skilling have shown that the Feynman rules are a necessary result of any probability represented by a pair of real numbers [15]. Goyal and Knuth have further shown that the Feynman rules can coexist free of conflict with conventional probability [12]. Earlier Sykora noted that quantum formulations uniquely contain a built-in measure, and reminded that while probabilities are routinely described in terms of a single number, a measure is also necessary. Though it is frequently not explicitly stated, the need for this second real number is never-the-less implied. He further demonstrated the crucial result that clear statement of the measure is necessary to eliminate ambiguities in evaluation of statistical data. [7].

Given that two real numbers are the minimum necessary to fully express a probability; given also that the Feynman rules are universally observed in nature when dealing with indistinguishable events; and given as well that the Feynman rules are the only two-component alternative to the Laplace rules that are compatible with them, we elect to treat Feynman's rules as a natural part of probability theory.

Feynman [14,16], citing von Neumann [17] has shown that in the quantum regime the introduction of a means of observation within a trajectory resets the arbitrary initial value θ_0 of the phase of the probability amplitude for the ongoing portion of the trajectory. As in a double slit experiment, let $p_F = |\varphi_1 + \varphi_2|^2$ be the probability of an event with two indistinguishable alternative ways of occurring, signified by the two subscripts. Suppose now that a means of observing each alternative is provided. The presence of the measuring equipment introduces arbitrary additive constants $\delta\theta_1$ and $\delta\theta_2$ to the phases of the probability amplitudes for ongoing events beyond the slits. Now $p_F = |\varphi_1 e^{i\delta\theta_1} + \varphi_2 e^{i\delta\theta_2}|^2$.

The multiple observations required to establish an observable probability p_F require that the phases of the alternatives be averaged over all angles. This results in reversion to the Laplace rule $p_L = |\varphi_1|^2 + |\varphi_2|^2$ as the sample size approaches infinity. Multiple observations have the effect of averaging over all initial assignments of past and future contributions to the probability. Von Neumann's phase reset was determined

based on the properties of the Dirac-von Neumann model of quantum mechanics. Given the long-term success of that model, we regard it as experimentally confirmed.

Now, until the possibility of an observation is present, an amplitude exists without a corresponding observable probability. Where observation is possible, the possibility of an observable probability emerges. The real valued probability is independent of the phase of its probability amplitude which is lost with the possibility of measurement. A new probability amplitude with new arbitrary initial phase describes the ongoing propagation.

It appears then that the Feynman rules constitute a natural replacement for the Laplace rules which follow from Feynman's when observation is possible.

The Path Integral

Let $\Delta\theta(t) = \int_{x(t)} dt [d\theta(t)/dt]$. This is the statistical distance traced by a particle as it traverses the trajectory $x(t)$. Let m be an arbitrary integer and let $\delta\theta = \Delta\theta/m$ so that $x[\theta(t)]$ is divided into m equally distinguishable segments.

Let p_j be the probability that the particle is found in the j^{th} segment when $x(t)$ calls for it to be there and measurement is possible. Let $\zeta_j \equiv p_j^{1/2}$. Then the probability amplitude for the j^{th} segment is $\varphi_j = \zeta_j e^{i\delta\theta}$.

From the amplitude product rule, the probability amplitude $\varphi_{x(t)}(BA)$ for a test particle following an arbitrary path $x(t)$ from A to B when the individual points cannot be observed, is the product of the probability amplitudes that the particle traverses every point on $x(t)$

$$\varphi_{x(t)}(BA) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{j=1}^m [\zeta_j e^{i\delta\theta}] = \exp \left\{ \int_A^B \frac{d \ln \zeta[x(\theta)]}{d\theta} d\theta + i\Delta\theta \right\} = \zeta_{x(t)} e^{i\Delta\theta} \quad (19)$$

where $\zeta_{x(t)}^2 = \left\{ \exp \int_A^B d\theta \frac{d \ln \zeta[x(\theta)]}{d\theta} \right\}^2 = \exp \int_A^B d\theta \frac{d \ln \zeta^2[x(\theta)]}{d\theta}$ is the probability that the path $x(t)$ is followed when observation of the path is possible.

We, know based on many decades of empirical experience verifying the Feynman formulation of non-relativistic quantum mechanics, that the proper expression for $\varphi_{x(t)}(BA)$ is [11]

$$\varphi_{x(t)}(BA) = \text{Const } e^{iS/\hbar} \quad (20)$$

where S is the classical action. Let us assume that the magnitude of the probability amplitude varies much more slowly than the phase, both along any trajectory and between points represented by the same value of the parameter t on adjacent trajectories. This is less restrictive than the Feynman prescription that the magnitude of the probability amplitude be the same for all trajectories. Then for trajectories of stationary phase, $\zeta_{x(t)}$ will be stationary as well and the substitution

$$S/\hbar = \Delta\theta \quad (21)$$

yields the Feynman result. The statistical distance $\theta(t)$ traced by a particle as it traverses $x(t)$ corresponds to the classical action $S(t)$ in units of \hbar while the rate of change of statistical distance with time $d\theta(t)/dt$ corresponds to the classical Lagrangian in units of \hbar .

$$\frac{L}{\hbar} \propto \frac{d\theta}{dt} = \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 \iint_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \left[\frac{d\zeta(x, t)}{dt} \right]^2 \right\}^{1/2} = \left\{ \left[\frac{da(t)}{dt} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{db(t)}{dt} \right]^2 \right\}^{1/2} \quad (22)$$

The probability that a test particle goes from start point A to end point B by any path is then computed according to the Feynman amplitude sum rule with the path integral replacing the summation in (16).

$$p(BA) = \left| \int \varphi_{x(t)}(BA) \mathcal{D}x(t) \right|^2 \quad (23)$$

This result constitutes the Feynman formulation of non-relativistic quantum mechanics as well as the principle of stationary action which we see corresponds to stationary statistical length $\Delta\theta(t)$ of the trajectory. From (8)

$$S = \Delta\theta = \int_{x(t)} dt \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 \iiint_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \left[\frac{d\zeta(x, t)}{dt} \right]^2 \right\}^{1/2} = \int_{x(t)} dt \frac{L}{\hbar} = \frac{S}{\hbar} \quad (24)$$

The Geodesic Principle

Our derivation of the Feynman formalism of non-relativistic quantum mechanics does not rely on the Euclidean nature of the physical space to which it is applied. A parallel derivation can be applied to a particle trajectory on a Lorentz manifold. General relativity is endowed with a well-defined action prescribing the motion of a particle as in the classical case. This leads directly to the extension of the Feynman formalism to gravitational theory.

Let $x^* = (x_0^*, x_1^*, x_2^*, x_3^*)$ represent the four-dimensional Lorentz manifold of general relativity, where x_0^* represents time multiplied by the speed of light while x_1^*, x_2^* and x_3^* represent the three spatial dimensions. Substituting x^* for x in (8) through (12) and specifying the proper time τ as the parameter of motion, we find, mutatis mutandis, the same definition of statistical distance. Continuing in the same vein through (19), we find the same expression for the probability amplitude of an arbitrary path in terms of the statistical length of the path $\Delta\theta^*$.

We proceed to substitute the relativistic action S^* for S . The classical action, when extended to the flat four-space of special relativity is $dS^* = mc ds$ where $m = E/c^2$ is the relativistic mass with E the total energy of the test particle, c the speed of light and s the distance traveled along the path in flat four space. This formulation is extended to the general relativistic case by acknowledging that the path is now through arbitrarily curved space where, employing the Einstein summation convention, $ds = (g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu)^{1/2}$ with $g_{\mu\nu}$ representing the metric tensor.

With action a known function of path length, we may define an element of length $l_h = h/mc$ characterizing dynamic uncertainty h as uncertainty in four-space location of a particle of relativistic mass m . This allows us to define the statistical path length

$$d\theta^* = dS^*/\hbar = 2\pi ds/l_h. \quad (25)$$

As before we can now substitute S^*/\hbar for $\Delta\theta^*$ in (19) and proceed to the path integral.

The statistical path length on the probability simplex is $\Delta\theta^* = \int_{x(\tau)} d\theta^*$. The path integral assures the value of $\Delta\theta^*$ represents an extremum. The corresponding path length on the Lorentz manifold is $\Delta s = \int_{x(t)} ds mc$.

Now in the rest frame of a test particle with rest mass m_0 , we have $m = m_0$ for all values of τ . Then by (25) the path length on the Lorentz manifold is proportional to the path length on the probability simplex. As a result, an extremum of the statistical path length $\Delta\theta^*$ corresponds to a geodesic on the Lorentz manifold independent of reference frame or coordinate system, whence the geodesic principle.

The Black Body Spectrum Revisited

When viewed in the laboratory frame, uncertainty of location in spacetime must appear as a small apparently random motion. This in turn results in a small zero-point energy. As early as 1913 employing purely classical analysis, Einstein and Stern showed that the assumption of zero-point energy $h\nu$ in Planck's dipole oscillators led to the Planck spectrum *without the independent assumption of energy quantization* [18].

Milonni has extended that analysis [18] noting each Planck oscillator is in synchronous equilibrium with an associated classical field mode of Planck's cavity. Employing the same zero-point energy $h\nu$, the equipartition theorem requires this energy be equally divided between oscillators and field, with each oscillator having energy $h\nu/2$ while its associated field mode contains equal energy $h\nu/2$.

Let us now momentarily assume that deterministic physical laws resembling those of classical physics continue to govern even at the microscopic level, subject to some undefined source of uncertainty in observed spacetime location. Each field mode is distributed over all of space and time, but is synchronized in all four dimensions with the associated oscillator. In this view, despite uncertainty in four-space location, the uncertainty produces no relative motion between oscillator and associated field mode. We would therefore expect no coupling between the zero-point motion of the dipole oscillator and the zero-point component of the field centered at what is necessarily the same location.

Returning to Milonni, still employing purely classical electromagnetic analysis, he demonstrates that when there is no interaction between the random components of the oscillator and the field, black body spectral density is

$$\rho(\nu) = \frac{8\pi h\nu^3/c^3}{e^{h\nu/kT} - 1} + 4\pi h\nu^3/c^3 \quad (26)$$

in agreement with quantum electrodynamic theory.

Though short of proof, Milonni's result suggests that even at the unobservable level, the concept of spacetime location accompanied by fully deterministic laws resembling the classical ones may prevail. It further suggests the possibility that in the unobservable domain, treatment of the electromagnetic field in the classical way can be a valid approach with quantization of the field being required to describe observable phenomena due to uncertainty in observation of spacetime location.

Discussion

The present analysis leads naturally to the Feynman formulation of non-relativistic quantum mechanics as a consequence of the empirical reality that the classical view of physical phenomena is inherently imperfect. Our analysis relies on an extended form of probability theory that employs the Feynman rules as the empirically determined rules of probability for indistinguishable events, reducing naturally to the Laplace rules when events can be distinguished.

A similar point of view can be applied to the Dirac-von Neumann formalism. Consistent with the " ψ -epistemic" view [19], the probability amplitude does not represent the state of the system. Instead, it represents the state of available information describing the system. When the amplitude is understood in this way, its collapse no longer represents a physical change in the system. Rather, it indicates the state of available information about the system has changed as the result of the possibility of measurement. An observable probability has emerged, while the probability amplitude has vanished, and a fresh probability amplitude characterizes future events.

The initial probability amplitude may be regarded as representing a conditional probability [12] based on the state of information prior to the possibility of measurement. The amplitude after measurement is possible represents a new conditional probability based on the new state of available information generated by that possibility.

Since the collapse of the wave function upon the possibility of measurement does not represent a change in the physical system, it may collapse at all points in space and time without the need to propagate at the speed of light. Because the physical system is unchanged, there is no reason to suppose a message has propagated instantaneously when a measurement in the laboratory affects the amplitude of a distant entangled particle. It is only what is known about the distant particle that has changed.

Goyal's analysis has shown [20] that the logic of the Feynman formalism is equivalent to that of Dirac-von Neumann when it is supplemented with a *no-disturbance postulate*. This posits that there exists a class of

trivial measurements which have no effect on the probability amplitude. Trivial measurements are defined by the property that they yield no new information about the system being measured.

This principle is a natural consequence of the epistemic interpretation of the probability amplitude, and constitutes strong evidence in support of it. With no change in information the conditional probabilities of subsequent outcomes are unchanged. Thus there is no change in the probability amplitude representing the state of available information.

Central to this view is that neither measurement, nor the possibility of measurement disturb the system. The no-disturbance postulate resides uncomfortably alongside the notion that uncertainty is caused by the process of measurement. It is hard to explain why an encounter with a quantum of radiation disturbs a system in a mixed state but not in an eigenstate. This peculiarity is avoided with the adoption of the ψ -epistemic viewpoint arising from the entropic origin of uncertainty.

The Wave Particle Duality

The historically empirical Laplace rules of probability among distinguishable alternatives have been shown here to lead naturally to the description of particle probabilities in terms of a complex probability amplitude with wavelike characteristics. With the adoption of the more general Feynman rules, empirically derived from observation of quantum phenomena, these probability amplitudes add as do the amplitudes of physical wave phenomena when observations of alternative events are not possible. This imparts wavelike properties to classical particles resulting strictly from the extended rules of probability.

Particle like behavior of classical electromagnetic waves with entropy empirically imposed by the observed black body spectrum was famously explored as early as 1905 [21, 22]. Einstein's classical analysis of the empirically determined high frequency portion of the black body spectrum found that the entropy of any narrow band or radiation about frequency ν matched that of an ideal molecular gas with particle energy concentrated in a narrow band around the value $h\nu$. Heuristic particle like behavior in classical wave phenomena thus provided a basis for understanding the photoelectric effect twenty years before the advent of modern quantum theory.

With the benefit of information theoretic insights not available for another half century [6] we have adopted a ψ -epistemic interpretation of that result. In this view the quantization of entropy leads to the quantization of information describing the electromagnetic fields rather than quantization of the fields proper.

A similar viewpoint may be adapted for massive particles. Quantum field theory describes matter in terms of unbounded fields similar to the description of electromagnetic radiation. In this view the probability represented by the amplitude is the probability of a particular field value or interaction at the prescribed location [23]. We may then view all particles as the potentially observable manifestations of underlying fields, representing quanta of information about field values and interactions.

This perspective alleviates some of the apparent mystery of quantum behavior. The Feynman rules underlying our view of probability theory appear less peculiar if it is understood that that they apply to an imperfect particle like vision of underlying wavelike phenomena. In this view, we see our notion of particles imperfectly substituting for quanta of information about the properties of underlying fields in a small volume of spacetime of approximate volume l_h^4 . At locations separated by spacetime distances much greater than l_h features of the amplitudes with width $\sim l_h$ representing events in the individual regions of uncertainty have minimal overlap. In this case the information carried by a particle is in one-to-one correspondence with the field in a unique distinguishable volume of four space. At these same scales quantum field theory has demonstrated remarkable fidelity to nature.

For locations separated by less than l_h regions of uncertainty are highly overlapped. Substitution of separate energetic particles for the field at a point in these overlapped regions becomes questionable since multiple particles now represent the field in parts of the same volume of four space multiple times, while multiple overlapping volumes are represented by the same particle.

We see computations of probabilities with quantum field theory that include events at separations much finer than l_h yield total probabilities greater than or less than unity [24, 25]. This provides motivation for limiting the inclusion of events to those separated by more than some distance of order l_h . Ultimately though, to properly model the situation, an improved computational approach seems desirable [25].

The Origin of Uncertainty

Perhaps the simplest explanation for the appearance of uncertainty can be found in the view that particles are an imperfect representation of quanta of information about fields. This view allows for underlying fields of all kinds [23], while all we can observe are particle like quanta of information about them. Canonically conjugate properties of these particles represent field properties that are each the Fourier transform of the other. Uncertainty is mathematically built into this relationship [26]. Indeed, it was this mathematical relationship that led Heisenberg to the uncertainty principle in the first place [27], though the meaning of the amplitude was far less explored than today.

This interpretation is an example of the *actually random* case represented by (3). We cannot view the fields directly, but only bundles of distinguishable quanta of information about them. These bundles of information have many of the properties of particles, but not all. When we imagine them as classical particles, a variety of peculiarities arise. Actual randomness is the most prominent arising from the simple result that uncertainty is a unique property of classical waves but not classical particles. Then, it is our preconception that particles have perfectly defined canonically conjugate properties that produces the belief we are seeing actually random behavior, though the underlying fields described by these bundles of quantized information may be deterministic as the Einstein, Stern, Milonni black body result suggests.

Further peculiarity arise centered around nonlocality. A field can propagate through two slits at the same time while a particle, as classically understood, cannot. We have shown that the Feynman rules form the basis for a self-consistent form of probability theory that can deal with this issue. Still the intrinsic concept of a particle that cannot be in two places at once is lost. Much of this can be made less peculiar by understanding the term particle to refer to a bundle of quantized information about underlying fields. The fundamental issue is that it takes more information to fully describe our common conception of a particles than to fully describe the underlying fields.

It is for now unclear whether there is also an alternative *apparently random* explanation of uncertainty consistent with (2) that would allow for full-fledged particles. What we can say about such a potential hidden variable theory is that Bell's theorem requires it to maintain nonlocality in the behavior of particles. In addition, its particle description contains more information than the "actually random" case. In view of this, Occam's razor favors the actually random view. We bear in mind that Occam's razor falls well short of proof, though it does provide substantial justification for using the view it favors as a working understanding until such time as new developments deem it untenable.

Emergence of the Geodesic Principle and Stationary Action

Regardless of the source of uncertainty, we have shown that for trajectories with piecewise differentiable probability amplitudes the principle of stationary action as well as the more general geodesic principle follow naturally from a small set of assumptions:

1. Natural phenomena are described in a Lorentz four-space model.
2. Observers of these phenomena experience some level of inherent uncertainty in their knowledge of location in this four-space.
3. The Feynman rules apply to the probability of physical phenomena when there are no means of distinguishing them.

We have argued that the Feynman rules constitute a more plausible empirically justified axiomatic basis for probability theory than the Laplace rules in that, at least when the probability is piecewise differentiable with respect to time, they cover a broader range of phenomena including both indistinguishable and distinguishable events. In the face of uncertainty at the observable level, these rules provide a mechanism for the deterministic laws of mechanics to emerge in the form of stationary action and the geodesic principle in which the path integral governs what we can observe.

Under these circumstances the probability amplitude of indistinguishable particle-like potentially-observable-entities that just happen to follow paths of near stationary length will be coherently enhanced. All others will be coherently suppressed. Thus, both the principle of stationary action, and the geodesic principle naturally emerge in an observable universe in which our assumptions hold sway, whence the foundation for much of what is observed in nature.

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